

ENGLISH AND UZBEK INTERPRETATIONS OF ZOOSEMISM IN PROVERBS

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Abstract: Each nation has proverbs based on their experience. In this article English and Uzbek proverbs are analyzed.

Key words: folklore, literature, culture, zoosemism, genre, figurative, phrase.

Annotatsiya: Har bir millat o'zining tajribasiga asoslangan maqollariga egadir. Bu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek maqollari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar : xalq og'zaki ijodi, adabiyot, madaniyat, zoni, janr, obrazli, iborat.

Аннотация: У каждого народа есть пословицы основанные на его опыте. В статье анализируются английские и узбекские пословицы.

Ключевые слова: фольклор, литература, культура, зоосемизм, жанр, образность, фраза.

Introduction: Nowadays, literature is also given great attention among many fields. The works of each poet and writer are a great heritage for future generations. Today, the folklore of the world and Uzbek literature is one of the precious masterpieces. Because, people's historical development, culture, outlook, artistic, creative and practical activities are described in ancient works which the community was made. This article talks about proverbs, another genre of folklore. Especially, using zoosemism term is analyzed in both folk proverbs by examples.

Main body: A deeper study of current proverbs is becoming more and more important today. The proverb is derived from the Arabic word means "to say" and "to tell". Proverbs are a genre of oral creativity, short, figurative, grammatical and a wise phrase with logical complete meaning, a wise phrase with a deep meaning. In proverbs, life experience of ancestors attitude to society, history, mental state, ethics the qualities of aesthetic feelings are embodied. Proverb of the people is a word of wisdom that comes through life experiences. In some proverbs, this is the meaning of animal names. This is one of the distinguishing features of both languages owner. Although, the name of the animal is not given in the following English proverbs, it acquires the meaning when translated in Uzbek language:

- When Hell freezes. Jahannam muzlaganda.
(Tuyaning dumi yerga tekkanda (o'zbek tilida muqobili))

In the next proverb on the contrary, the given proverb in English don't express the meaning directly:

- Go to bed with the lamb, and the rise with the lark.

Erta turgan ishini bitirar, kech turgan ko'p turtinar.

In this proverb, unlike the above proverbs in both languages express the same meaning:

- Better be the head of a dog than the tail of a lion.

Arslonning dumi bo'lgandan itning boshi bo'lgan yaxshi.

The following proverbs, the image of a **dog** reveals the negative characteristics of people in a negative sense, while in English proverbs on the contrary it remains in a positive sense.

- Two **dogs** over one bone seldom agree.

(Itidan suyak ortmas, mushukdan bez)

- A **dog** will not howl if you beat him with a bone.

Itni suyak bilan ursangiz qopmas.

And above mentioned two proverbs, the image of a **dog** is more angry, careless, bad, dirty, it is aimed at corrupt, greedy, ambitious people.

- A good **dog** deserves a good bone.

Yaxshi itga yaxshi suyak.

- Give a **dog** a bad name and hang him.

Itga yomon nom bergin-u, osgin.

In this case, the image of a dog represents loyalty, devotion, goodness, wisdom and honestly embodied.

Our next analysis is the analysis of zoosemism in the image of each animal meanings are revealed.

- A barleycorn is better than a diamond to a **rooster**.

Xo'roz uchun arpa olmosdan yaxshiroqdir.

- All is **fish** that comes to his net.

Nimaiki ilinsa to'riga, baliq bo'lib ko'rinar ko'ziga.

(Tovuqning tushiga don kirar (manfaat)) (In the case of fish and chicken.)

- **Fish** begins to stink at the head.

Baliq boshidan sasiydi.

(Poor management in the image of fish)

- A **bird** never flew on one wing.

Qush hech qachon bitta qanotda uchmaydi.

- A closed mouth catches no **flies**.

Yopiq og'iz chivinlarni tutmaydi.

- The great **fish** eat up the small.
Katta baliq kichik baliqni yeydi.
(Zo'rga ham zo'rdek balo bor)
- Like water off a **duck's** back.
Suv o'rdakning patidan sirg'alib tushganidek.
(Dunyoni suv bossa,o'rdakka nima g'am).
- Kill the **goose** that laid the golden eggs.
Oltin tuxum qo'yadigan g'ozni o'ldirmoq.
(O'zing suv ichadigan quduqqa tupurma)
- A **dog** wants doggy discipline.
It itning intizomini xoxlaydi.
- A **donkey** laden with gold is still but a donkey.
Oltin yuklangan eshak hali ham eshakdir.
- All **cats** love fish but fear to wet their paws.
Mushuk baliqni xush ko'rar ammo oyog'ini ho'llashdan qo'rqrar.
(Baliqni xush ko'rgan qiltanog'idan qo'rqmas)
- When the **cat's** away, the mice will play.
Mushuk ketsa,sichqon o'yinga tushadi.
(Mushukning o'limi sichqonga to'y)
- **Rats** desert a sinking ship.
Kalamushlar cho'kayotgan kemadan qochadi.
(Xoin xavfli bo'ladi)
- At open doors **dogs** come in.
Ochiq eshikka itlar kirar.
(Hushyorni yov bosmas,yov bossa ham,dov bosmas)
- If you keep a **dog**, don't beat yourself up.
Agar it boqsang,o'zing hurima.
- **Birds** of a feather flock together.
Qushlar bir joyga to'planar.
- When the **fox** preaches , then beware your geese.
Tulki nasihat qila boshlaganida,g'ozlaringizni qo'riqlang.
(Tulkining hiylasi ko'p yaxshisi qochmoq)
- An **ass** in a lion's skin.
Sher terisidagi eshak.
(Kalla boshqa,salla boshqa)(maqtanchoqlik)

- Catch the **bear** before you sell his skin.
Ayiqning terisini sotishdan oldin o'zini tutgin.
(Sabr-toqat)

It can be seen that in English and Uzbek proverbs given above is described the positive and negative characteristics, qualities and spiritual experience of giving we have analyzed only a part that can be expressed. In this case, in English and Uzbek proverbs human qualities and characteristics are also described. This term is used in the interpretation of the image of an animal description ensures that figurative meanings are expressed in literature.

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